

Greener Journal of Psychology and Counselling

Submission Date: 18/12/013

Accepted: 15/08/014

Published: 19/08/014

Reviewing the Skeletons of the Politics of Science; A Continuing Debate on Homosexuality as a Depathologised Diagnosis

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Review Article

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ABSTRACT

This paper is an attempt to re- explore and objectively revisit APA's decision to remove homosexuality from the diagnostic statistical manual of mental disorders and the ramifications of the decision over the years.. It asserts that many life events are being manipulated by belief systems. The influence of cultures is overarching, affecting people in more ways than they realize, especially in the patterns of their everyday lives. When there are too many of these unthinking habits affecting actions, there is an ensuing discrepancy between thought and action. The argument is that the relationship between science and politics cause many communications about the Diagnostic Statistical Manual of mental disorders (DSM) to be mired in controversy. The DSM took science for granted and allowed the whims of politics to rule thereby creating an unending controversy where homosexuality serves as an affirmation of that which was and is being denied the chance of scientific scrutiny. This has been evidenced in the issue of the removal of homosexuality as a pathology, which has continued to create points of discussion in different settings and forums. It is argued that when one enters the realm of politics, objectivity loses its aura and science become far removed and contested. The historical struggle to remove homosexuality from the DSM informs its current sustenance as a contested diagnosis.

Keywords: Diagnostic Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Homosexuality, Paraphilias, Politics of science.

INTRODUCTION

"Sex lies at the root of life and we can never learn with reverence, life, until we know how to understand sex" (Havelock as quoted in preface to Janowisky, 1898).

Studying sex has always been difficult, there is general misinformation about sex matters, and sex is stigmatised, private and has ethical considerations. In like manner and as a consequence, the field of sexual disturbances has tended to be clouded in confusion and mystery as stated by Socarides (1973). One facet of human sexual behaviour that is so obvious and needs no research program to establish its truths is that some sexual activities are judged as undesirable and change worthy (Laws and Donohue, 1997). This is true to the field of psychiatric diagnosis which has been dubbed the child of morality and religious values controlling psychiatric practice (Silverstein, 1977).

The number of prohibitions and the importance attached to sexual behaviours is considered one of the most destructive tendencies of human sexuality. This is just but one view. The other view questions the very grounds humans in general or mental health professions in particular either do or should evaluate sexual practices. Shornewolf as quoted in Langer and Martin (2004) brings to the fore the idea that denial is a strong current in human beings and that there is always a tendency in human beings to deny problems and even deny one's disorder as an abnormality. Laws and Donohue espouse that lack of a well supported criterion upon which to distinguish permissible or healthy sexual behaviour is related to the inability of mental health professionals to make demarcations of what is normal or abnormal. If indeed religion and morality are the foundation of psychiatric theory and the practice concerning sexual behaviour, there is need to continue questioning the process of the removal of homosexuality from the book of disorders. If other sexual behaviours (paraphilias) are still included as mental disorders then the very reasons for removing homosexuality remain flimsy (Bayer, 1981). It is on these bases that we have Moser and Kleinplatz (2006) argue for the removal of paraphilias. Such arguments were never objectively given in the earlier case (Silverstein, 2009) and it can then be extrapolated that in these arguments lie the bases of the protracted case of the removal of homosexuality from the American Psychiatry Association's Diagnostic Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM). The impact was to have far reaching consequences to the understanding, research and therapy of severe sexual disorders, among other things. Mendelson (2003) aptly posits that accepting the social and political factors that contributed to the removal of homosexuality insinuates accepting the social and political factors that still regard homosexuality as

a disorder. The concept of homosexuality as a psychopathology should continue being critically analysed to determine if it meets the criterion of mental disorder as presented in the DSM. Clearly, the politics of the present day suggest acceptance for the sake of liberating non - conforming people (Ault and Brzuzy 2009) and the broader changes in cultural beliefs about homosexuality that came as a result of its removal from psychopathology (Dreshler 2012).

The DSM is an important resource for mental health professionals with a primary influence in the United States and also with a wider global impact. The American Medical Association Statistics (2002) points out that the DSM is the most widely used diagnostic reference book and every single physician in the United States refers to this book to code for a diagnosis. APA in the preface to DSM1V –TR 4th edition (2000) elaborates that the use of the diagnostic codes is fundamentally for record keeping, enhances data collection, retrieval and compilation of statistics. It also states that diagnostic sub-categories increase specificity and that the DSM is applied to a current presenting condition and not to a previous diagnosis from which an individual has already recovered from. APA (2009) points out that diagnoses through the DSM facilitates communication among professionals or standardises research parameters. DSM's practice guidelines principally provide evidence based recommendations for the treatment of psychiatric disorders.

APA (2000) outlines that the American Psychiatric Association was founded in 1844 and claims to be the largest psychiatric body representing 38000 psychiatric professionals in mental health. These members share common interest in the continuing study of psychiatry and search for more effective ways to combat mental illness and ensure medical diagnosis and treatment for all persons with mental disorders. They achieve this by using the DSM as a common reference.

From the onset, it can be noted that any change in the manual (DSM) has far reaching consequences yet its history has been one of continuous evolution; and APA in DSM1V-TR (2000) notes that the most challenging issue for diagnosis is establishing the exclusion criteria for mental health diagnoses. There seems to be an overlap between normal and abnormal health behaviours and between different types of diagnoses. It is hereby noted that the issue of deciding whether a particular behaviour can be termed normal or disordered has been an elusive one and still doges the field and practice of mental health today as it was when APA initially established the first diagnostic manual over half a century ago.

The APA website (2009) traces the origins of the DSM dating back from an 1840 census inclusion of idiocy and insanity frequency to the post world war publication of ICD 1 by the World Health Organisation (WHO), it also chronicles historical milestones like the ICD 6-variant which is regarded as the first edition of the DSM. DSM 1 contained a glossary of descriptions of diagnostic categories. DSM-11 revised this with explicit definitions of the disorders as a means for promoting reliable clinical diagnoses. It was after this point that the notion to remove homosexuality as a mental disorder was mooted. Homosexuality was subsequently removed from the DSM111 in 1975 which saw the introduction of methodological innovations, explicit diagnostic criteria, a multi-axial system and a descriptive approach neutral to theories of aetiology. The DSM11-r in 1987 cleared the inconsistencies produced by earlier changes to the manual. The DSM1V of 1994 had comprehensive review of literature review to establish a form empirical basis for diagnosis. Other additions were later added to the DSM1V-TR and the current and latest edition of the DSM is the DSM 5 (APA, 2012).

BACKGROUND POLITICS

Homosexuality is an enduring attraction to or sexual behaviour between people of the same sex or to a sexual orientation. Moser and Kleinplatz (2006) explains it as a sense of personal and social identity based on these attractions, behaviours expressing them in a community of others who share them, probably the difference in perceptions on what is homosexuality was to be the first sticking point leading to its exclusion from the DSM but, so were and still are many other mental disorders that are difficult to describe and define. This may explain why DSM 1 had undergone six reprints by October 1973 and the DSM has been amended several times since then. Socarides (1978) argues that the problem of homosexuality had been criminal discrimination but however, repealing of punitive laws against homosexuals would not remove their inner anxieties. This argument was based on the fact that the difference between sexual deviations could not be blurred without incurring formidable scientific chaos.

For many years the mental health professionals had considered homosexuality to be a disease but the land DSM 111 came to regard homosexuality that is accepted by the individual as a sexual interest and therefore not disordered (Schindleim, 2004). Confusion still reigns within the profession on whether homosexuality is not a disorder or not despite the current DSM position that it is not. The removal is therefore critiqued for lack of consistency with the same DSM text (Ault and Brzuzy 2009). It seems APA itself is still divided over the issue in principle although in practice they are bound to the DSM. Should it be said that the decision to exclude homosexuality from the DSM left the APA divided on how to categorise and diagnose sexual mental health pathologies.

The DSM1V Tr continues to be vague and does not explain what is non-social and occupational functioning, terms used to exclude a homosexual behaviour as pathologies. It states that there must be significant occupational and social functioning and must be associated with present distress not socially

or culturally sanctioned. However it can be argued that given the negative attitudes and the stigmatisation, homosexuality could still be regarded as a mental disorder as it causes impairment in social and occupational functioning. This is still inconsistent with the framework of the DSM definition. The current DSM, like its predecessors ignores the relations with others contributing to cause impairments and ignores the fact that a mental disorder is not only disturbed but a disturbing behaviour (Schiendleim, 2004). The DSM is not consistent and in the same way it could not later distinguish paraphilic and non - paraphilic behaviours and hence the subsequent removal of the later category from the DSM. Shacht (1985) had earlier alluded to these discrepancies and recent calls for the removal of gender identity disorder seem to be rooted in this argument (Ault and Brzydu 2009).

THE POLITICAL WAR WITHIN THE FIELD AND THE PROFESSION

Socarides (1978) describes the intellectual confusion and diagnostic inconsistency which led to the removal of homosexuality from the DSM. The impact was one of shaking the foundation of the profession of psychiatry leaving it divided as the removal implied that homosexuality has no clinical symptoms and no course of development over time and therefore cannot be treated. Others argued then and many others still do, that using the social disadvantage criterion established by APA itself, homosexuality would still be a mental disorder. Socarides also points out that homosexuality is only viewed as abnormal when only the one who practices it is disturbed by it. The impact for the profession of mental health was to disregard the DSM and consequently moving away from the need for diagnosis by the practitioner into the field of self diagnosis by individuals which is subjective and unscientific. APA then began moving away from the dictates of science, it can be argued.

The argument put forward is that APA, confronted with overwhelming empirical evidence and cultural views of homosexuality took a political decision over the scientific issue and changed its views (Berude, 1990). Military research showed that well adjusted individuals could conceal their orientation and make credible records for themselves in the service (Berude, 1990). The notion was then that homosexuals in general can lead productive useful lives conforming to all the dictates of community except its sexual requirements. However this is not supported by events and process as APA went on further to remove homosexuality completely from the DSM by 1986 without any additional substantive evidence or carrying out an investigation to substantiate the arguments (Schiendleim, 2004). The impact is for it to appear as if APA began to decide issues on a vote system as opposed to basing decisions exclusively on landmark studies. The voting system is in the realm of politics and the impact of politics in scientific decisions began to take root. It can still be argued that APA was influenced by vociferous gay rights movement to make the initial and latter decisions. The vote was not on whether homosexuality is a disorder or not but on whether to continue treating it as one or not. The impact of the APA vote was for the rest of the world to think that it was based on the earlier question and therefore distort the world view of homosexuality as normal and that is validated by APA (Spitzer, 1974).

From a medical perspective, in which APA is firmly embedded, official assertions and decisions should always be based on clinical features. Janowisky (1898) pointed out that there was and still probably is in over a century from his time, insufficient knowledge contained about this behaviour (homosexuality), basically because of the incorrectness of many of the guiding principles of the examination into the actual circumstance of homosexuality, the absence of well defined symptoms existing concurrently with homosexuality and other supposed derangements of the nervous system has compounded research findings since Janowisky's time. The impact has been to shift focus from seeing homosexuality not so much as an organic anomaly such as syphilis but rather as a disease of morality. The APA believes that it was formed for mental illness diagnosis and treatment and the movement away from criminalisation of homosexuality may have impacted on it to remove this not so medical but rather social condition from its diagnostic books.

However, as Janowisky pointed out, there is vast difference between homosexuality and other normal sexual behaviours as shown through findings that there is or maybe a genetic link of some sort in sexual deviancy. For example, in relation to a male homosexual, it is stated that:

"The sight of a naked young woman leaves him indifferent whereas that of a man will awaken in feelings of lust..... The representation of a woman gives rise to no excitation but paralyse the voluptuous feeling when such already exist... just as a normally sexually developed men cannot feel any desire for another man, so it is equally impossible for the homosexual to accomplish coitus with a woman"(Janowisky, 1898, p13).

The issue for APA was then to decide whether such genetic difference in behaviour exhibition without any substantial empirical evidence for such difference in organic terms was enough to make a diagnosis. The issue for debate on homosexuality has always been of science versus social factors- the nature nurture debate. The acknowledgement by other practising homosexuals that they were abnormal and were trapped in female bodies have cultural and moral connotations and may also have led APA to choose to let go of homosexuality from the DSM, through a social decision.

RESOLVING THE IMPASSE THROUGH ROUNDTABLE NEGOTIATION

Socarides (1978) details that the matter had to be resolved by a referendum of 243 psychiatrists and fellows of APA. Whether or not there had been pressure for these fellows to vote in a particular way is irrelevant as it cannot be proven. The impact is that APA decided to give in to the social realm of the environment in which it was operating at the time and inevitably to look into the social aspects of its diagnoses, a stance that is still manifesting itself in latest editions of the DSM. The argument is that basically APA revised a basic code of life and biology that normally men and women mate with the opposite sex. The increase in visibility and acceptance of homosexuality in some constitutions and legal policies in some parts of the world all seem to support that a false step amounted to an approval and encouragement of homosexuality. Bayer as quoted in the TVC special report (2000p.3), seem to agree to the necessity of the move on homosexuality by stating that "the result of APA removal of homosexuality from the DSM was not a conclusion based upon an approximation of scientific truth but was instead an action demanded by the ideological temper of the times".

It can also be argued that to this day, the impact after the decision has been to incorporate prevailing ideologies at the time of each DSM version's incorporation defining categories of diagnoses. Rights issues have seen increased illumination and presence in latest definitions of diagnoses. The impact of the removal of homosexuality from DSM dented the image of APA as a scientific organisation. It is reported that APA held parties afterwards to celebrate this gay victory (socarides, 1978). How an impartial scientific organisation could celebrate its decision unless they had become partial and transformed into activists is a point of debate. This certainly led to the question whether scientific findings should be dismissed for social and political reasons. Debate has been raging on whether APA blatantly disregarded and invalidated thousands of research papers of serious studies for the past century in favour of striking off homosexuality from the list of mental disorders.

Stainton and Stainton (2000) alludes that homosexuality is abnormal and against all biological, evolutionary and genetic inheritance theories and link it to the gay and the queer or rebellious body theory. Most coming out models presume that awareness of same sex attraction emerges in early adulthood before age 10 and that awareness and exploration of same sex attraction that takes place during adolescence and eventually results in an integration of a homosexual identity into personality (Heath and Macintosh, 2000 as quoted in Schindleim, 2004). APA seems to be validating research to the contrary such as those quoted in Villareal (2006). It was stated that homosexuality is not a clinical entity and that it is inherently associated with psychopathology. Recent research has indicated that there is a statistically significant relationship between internalised oppression and depression and that there is no relationship between oppression and mental health (Majied, 2003). From the perspective of this finding, it is then argued that it is somewhat pathological. Ervin (2005) outlines that aspects of male gender role conflict and internalised homo negativity significantly impacted global and scientific dimensions of gay psychological well being. Some form of pathology in homosexuality is hereby propounded. On the whole, research and theory provide parallel analyses and conflicting results on homosexuality.

RAMIFICATIONS OF THE VOTE AND ITS FAR REACHING EFFECTS

There are those who argue against the politicisation of APA and state that the research and development council of APA did not investigate or study the issue before it gave formal approval for the removal of homosexuality from the DSM (Moser and Kleinplatz, 2005). The point is that dominant views of the leaders of APA at a specific point in time are passed down as views of APA in the documents produced at that time and the most far reaching changes are always thus made through political jockeying and finally represented in the diagnostic manuals.

It is also argued that there was clinical fallout and silencing of those who wished to retain homosexuality as a valid diagnosis through lectures, meetings and publications since 1973. To this day the foregoing has made it difficult for similarly renegade opinions and voices to be heard as APA commands worldwide respect that any dissenters are never given recognition and seldom listened for their arguments' worth (Schindleim, 2004). There was and still is also widespread use of political parties, religious leaders to reinforce the silence as Socarides (1978) pointed out and this trend shows no sign of abating in the present day as shown by legalising homosexuality and making dissenters liable against national political laws.

If psychiatric residents are more reluctant to enter an area of psychiatric research in homosexuality, where if they do not toe the line they will be attacked, belittled or demeaned, what are the implications? The result could have been the neglect of the field of homosexuality as a primary focus of study organically and subsequently there has been little or no increase in knowledge on what causes homosexuality or whether it is an organic disorder or just a social phenomenon. The long time impact is one of reducing spontaneity in sexual research, making other topics taboo and inadvertently stunting scientific knowledge production. Studies have indicated that there is also homosexuality in animals but the motivators of these behaviours and their implications have yet to be fully understood and may well never be. It has to be accepted that humans have a greater sexual diversity and engage in non-productive sex even with their opposite sex mates, facts the scientific community and the world at large have previously been unwilling to accept (APA, 2009).

Friends and families of Ex-Gays (2009) point out that the APA vote served as a Trojan horse, opening gates to widespread psychological and social change in customs and mores. They further argue that it was a

blow to homosexuals who had looked to psychiatry for help. Self esteem and emotional distress maybe general outcomes of gay identity development that in turn influence variables more directly related to AIDS risk behaviour (Smith, 1997). While considered as a homophobic attack against homosexuality, the link of homosexuality to HIV/AIDS prevalence seems to have empirical validity. Could then the impact of homosexuality's removal from the DSM have been the rapid increase in HIV/AIDS epidemic in later decades? This assertion is a partial view in the complex HIV/AIDS debate and needs to be validated by research.

Whilst there are countries that still outlaw homosexuality such as Zimbabwe and other still punish it by death as Iran and parts of Nigeria today, most countries have followed APA decision to accept the sexual behaviour as an individual choice. However it should be noted that even in such latter countries, homosexuality is abhorred by many. APA has remained on the forefront of subsequent homosexual debate milestones. In January 2005, the European Union (EU) approved a resolution banning homophobia and the legalisation of homosexual marriages and civil unions throughout Europe (TVC report, 2006). This was on the basis of recommendations and support from APA. There is ongoing debate on the need to allow homosexual couples the right to adopt children. The basis of the arguments is that the rights of children to have a home will further be enhanced since homosexuality is also considered normal (legally). In essence this is a continuation of the impact of, and the Pandora's box opened by the removal of homosexuality from the DSM. However, obstacles lie in the possibility of child abuse and because APA is not mandated to decide on legal issues such as adoption, the vigil by homosexuals in this regard may last a little longer before their activism bears fruit.

Debate is raging why all the other deviations are still in the DSM following removal of homosexuality. Most of them are similar to homosexuality and would benefit from the pardoning criteria that befell homosexuality. Paraphilias have also been removed from the DSM-IV-TR IN 2000 based on the critique that there was no logic, consistency, clarity on whether it constituted a mental disorder with little evidence to support its inclusion (Giles, 2000). The essence is that removal of homosexuality has led to the review of other diagnoses, especially linked to sexuality possibly led to the DSM being revised so many times.

For example, social workers have also led a drive or activism to have child gender identity disorder removed from DSM-IV-TR (Langer and Martin, 2004). They argue that gender identity disorder is a social construction, as is homosexuality, and varies overtime and according to culture and social class. The argument for social workers is thus hinged on the same arguments that drove the movement (APA) to drop homosexuality from DSM, IE there is no evidence of deviancy except statistically and that distress is socially imposed. If APA has categorically stated that homosexuality is not to be considered a mental disorder, there is no social rationality for preventing a child from being homosexual as the gender identity disorder seems to have been tailored to achieve. This is a test case for APA, for not considering the similar merits of the social workers argument may validate scepticism building around the credibility of APA. Langer and Martin went further to assert that this (social workers) is an example of the trend towards normalising not just sexual and gender disorders but disorders in general. The impact of removal of homosexuality therefore seems to be that it was a leading case in the dismantling of the DSM.

The wave of opinion against APA is still based on charges that it bows down political activism, serving neither the goals of neither individual liberties nor those of society. It is also felt that APA has retrogressed and removed entire areas of scientific progress rendering chaotic fundamental truths about mental health and particularly the interrelationship between anatomy and psychosexual identity (Socarides, 1978). This is an inadvertent outpouring of the impact of that single decision of the removal of homosexuality way back then in 1973.

Even the United States military was forced to revise its laws and policies on employment after a vicious outcry from the media. Pentagon retreated and issued statement that pointed out that they would indeed implement the changes necessary but the imposition of these conditions would have a practical impact (Giles, 2000). This indicates the social unwillingness to make the decision by APA a global phenomenon and a noting of far reaching consequences. For example, the military would have to deal with cases of sodomy and unwelcome sexual attraction and even change its old aged acts and laws that make them distinct and total institutions in the first place. The suddenness for the immediacy for change unnerved the military as it did many other voiceless social citizens.

While an equal access to health was guaranteed to homosexuals and recognition and legal right later became enshrined in laws, the issues of parenting became paradoxical as most parents still do not want to raise their children to be homosexuals in the same mould as they would accept other homosexual marriages. There are others who argue that the impact of APA's decision on homosexuality might have even added to pathologies in the mental health as it did not address the social stigma and discrimination aspects. There is a likelihood that cases of depression, suicide, negative stereotyping and a higher incidence of mental disorders among homosexuals themselves might have consequence, as APA (2009) acknowledges.

CONCLUSION: A POLITICS OF SCIENCE DEBATE

Socarides is quoted in the American medical association statistics lamenting that APA's decision on homosexuality is a chilling reminder that if scientific principles are not fought for, they can be lost in the snares of

political factionalism. One gets the sense that there was growing disillusionment among psychiatrists that the organisation APA was not for them, but against them scientifically. The sense of political decision making evokes the image of majority versus minority camps in APA's structures and the feeling of increasing use of power instead of evidence on the part of APA. The Myth that psychiatry has proven that homosexuality is normal is against scientific ethics of finding evidence before any proclamation. Minority psychiatrists still believe that there is none available to the cause of homosexuality's removal from the DSM and its subsequent loss of the pathological tag. Medicine undertakes to save the honour of mankind before the court of morality and individuals from being judged by God and their fellow men (Ebbing as quoted in Janowisky, 1898). APA'S decision on homosexuality seems to have sunk the field into more confusion of that which it claims to make clear. For how else can one explain the intense controversy and intricacies that have followed that decision over forty years on? Such is the case bedevilling the present day Anglican church on whether or not to ordain gay bishops and priests. All blame is put on the decision maker and as such, APA has to live with the impact of the fallout. Yet another impact of the removal of homosexuality from the DSM has been to further question the cross-cultural applicability of the DSM. Clearly, from the homosexuality and paraphilias cases, what is considered acceptable in the United States is viewed as stigmatised in other cultures. The shortcoming of the DSM in universalising diagnoses is therefore exposed.

No society has ever considered adult preferential homosexuality, despite APA 's decision to remove it as a diagnostic category and laws enforcing its legality. Kinsey studies as reported in Vilareal (2006) points out that negative personal attitude towards homosexuality persist. Nowhere is homosexuality a desired end in itself. This is a slap in the face of the decision to remove it from the DSM (parents and friends of the ex gays, 2009) event, though there is lack of empirical evidence and professional norms to validate homosexuality which to many is not a form of mental illness linked to psychopathology. Psychology today claims to work from a value free philosophy, but therapists ganged up and decided to choose the removal of homosexuality for their clients unifying and redefining sexuality with masculine and feminine identity.

APA voted for the endorsement of homosexual marriages in 2005 (Moser and Kleinplatz, 2006) and must now the institution of marriage be redefined to suit a group and should not definitions come out of spontaneous activity not consciously manipulated? Has APA become an activist organisation itself by its continuous engagement in support of homosexuality? These questions will continue to demand answers from APA as a consequence of its earlier homosexuality decision and latter endorsements in its support. The role of politics in science cannot be denied and the extent it then impacts science/ mental health and its practice deserves to be further researched on. The vote of hands for the removal of homosexuality was clearly a political one and not an objective vote as Bayer (1981) as quoted in Silverstein (2009) indicates in discussing the complete account of the meeting and subsequent political conflict leading to the recommendation.

However, that modern attitudes towards homosexuality have social, religious, legal and medical underpinnings cannot be denied; that psychological constructs more so about sexuality are notoriously difficult to measure and diagnose; and that there has been failure to find therapies for most sexual aspects of mental health, may all have been precipitated and or made clear by the decision to remove homosexuality from the DSM, is a widely held view. The impact of the removal of homosexuality from the DSM has been far reaching and varied, positively and negatively depending on one's standpoint. That it has led to increase in HIV & AIDS statistics (Brookmeyer, 1991) is a case against and that it has helped leverage human right campaigns and wide acceptance of gays including non-discrimination in housing and employment (Silverstein 1977 as quoted in Silverstein 2009) is a positive point. That it was a political decision may be a fact that may have its disputers, but that it will continue to shape and influence and impact events seem more plausible than the earlier. Arguments for and against the removal of homosexuality from the DSM remain equally strong and militating, creating an arena for the politics of science to rage on. This objective scrutiny should still see the light of day however, unpalatable it may appear especially coming against the grain of modern political trends. The skeletons of the view of homosexuality as pathological persist especially that wide acceptance should not mean it becomes less offensive to some. This rings true to the case of pornography, whose wide acceptance over the internet has not abated calls for its ban as offensive in public realms. In the words of Silverstein (1977), even science can benefit from past mistakes.

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Cite this Article: Chimunhu J, 2014. Reviewing the Skeletons of the Politics of Science; A Continuing Debate on Homosexuality as a Depathologised Diagnosis. *Greener Journal of Psychology and Counselling*, 1 (1): 001-007.